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DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF RP-HPLC METHOD FOR AMLODIPINE, CHLORTHALIDONE AND OLMESARTAN IN SOLID DOSAGE FORM

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ABSTRACT

To develop and validate simple and rapid isocratic reversed-phase high-performance liquid chromatography method (RP-HPLC) for the simultaneous estimation of Amlodipine, Chlorthalidone and Olmesartan in synthetic mixture. The chromatographic separation was achieved by using mobile phase Methanol and Phosphate Buffer adjusted with Sodium Hydroxide (pH 5) (80:20 v/v), Hypersil BDS C₁₈ column (250 mm x 4.6 mm, 5 µm particle size). The mobile phase was pumped at a flow rate of 1.0ml/min and the eluents were monitored at 238nm. Retention times were 5.503 min, 3.107 min and 3.980 min for Amlodipine, Chlorthalidone and Olmesartan respectively. Linearity was observed in the concentration range of 2.5-7.5 µg/ml, 6.25-18.75 µg/ml and 10-30 µg/ml for Amlodipine, Chlorthalidone and Olmesartan respectively. The percentage recoveries found to be as for Amlodipine 98.03-101.22 %, Chlorthalidone 98.97-101.38 % and Olmesartan 98.37-101.76 % respectively. All the parameters are validated as per ICH guidelines for the method validation and found to be suitable for routine quantitative analysis in pharmaceutical dosage forms.

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INTRODUCTION

Amlodipine is calcium channel blocker and is used as an anti-hypertensive, Which is chemically describe as 3-ethyl 5-methyl 2-[(2-aminoethoxy) methyl]-4-(2-chlorophenyl)-6-methyl-1,4-dihydropyridine-3,5-dicarboxylate .It is a dihydropyridine calcium channel blocker. It inhibits cellular influx of calcium, thus causing vasodilation. It has greater selectivity for vascular smooth muscle [1]. Olmesartan is Angiotensin II Type 1 Receptor Blockers and is used as an anti-hypertensive, which is chemically described as (5-methyl-2-oxo-1,3-dioxol-4-yl)methyl 4-(1-hydroxy-1-methylethyl)-2-propyl-1-{{2'-(2H-tetrazol-5-yl)biphenyl-4-yl}methyl}-1H-imidazole-5-carboxylate .It is an ARB it selectively inhibits the binding of angiotensive II to AT1 that is found in many tissues for example vascular smooth muscle and the adrenal glands. It is effectively inhibits AT1- mediated vasoconstriction and aldosterone secreting special effects of angiotensin II and its results to reduction vascular resistance and blood pressure [2]. It is selective for AT1 also that 12,500 times greater affinity for AT1 than the AT2 receptor. Chlorthalidone is Sodium chloride symporter inhibitors and used as an anti-hypertensive agent and diuretic, Which is chemically describe as (RS)-2-chloro-5-(1-hydroxy-3-oxo-2, 3-dihydro-1H-isindol-1-yl) benzene-1-sulfonamide.It prevents sodium ion transport across the renal tubular epithelium in cortical diluting segment of ascending limbs of henle. As increasing the delivery of sodium to distal renal tubule that ultimately increased potassium excretions via sodium- potassium exchange mechanism [3]. Literature review indicated that many spectrophotometric and HPLC method were reported for individual drug and in combination with other drugs. So, the aim of present study was to develop a simple, rapid, precise, accurate and selective chromatographic method for the estimation of Amlodipine, Olmesartan and Chlorthalidone in synthetic mixture [4-13].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemicals and Reagents:

Amlodipine, Olmesartan and Chlorthalidone procured from Umedica Laboratories pvt ltd. HPLC grade methanol was purchased from Lichrosolv- E. Merck (India) Ltd. Mumbai.

Instrumentation:

High Performance Liquid Chromatography:

Model: Shimadzu

Software: LC solution

Column: Hypersil BDS C18 (4.6mm*250mm) 5 μ m

Pump: Isocratic

Wavelength range: 200-800 nm

Detector: UV-VIS detector

Chromatographic conditions

1. Stationary Phase: Hypersil BDS C18 (4.6mm*250mm), 5 μ m was used at ambient temperature
2. Mobile phase: Phosphate Buffer (pH-5): methanol: water (80:20 % v/v)
3. Flow rate: 1.0ml/min
4. Injection volume: 20 μ L
5. Detection: At 238 nm with UV visible detector

Standard solution and calibration graphs for chromatographic measurement

Accurately weighed 100 mg Amloipine, 50 mg, Olmesartan and Chlorthalidone were transferred to 100 ml volumetric flask. It was dissolved with sufficient methanol and diluted up to mark with methanol to give concentration of 1000 μ g/ml of Amlodipine, 1000 μ g/ml of Amlodipine,Olmesartan and Chlorthalidone. 0.5 ml of this solution was further diluted to 10 ml with methanol to get 50 μ g/ml of Amloipine, 0.125 ml of Chlorthalidone dilute up to 10 ml with methanol to get 125 μ g/ml of Chlorthalidone and 2ml of Olmesartan solution was further diluted to 10 ml with methanol to get 200 μ g/ml of Olmesartan. Above solution was diluted further to get the concentration range of 2.5-7.5 μ g/ml, 6.25-18.75 μ g/ml and 10-30 μ g/ml for Amlodipine , Chlorthalidone and Olmesartan respectively .Peak areas were plotted against the corresponding concentrations to obtain calibration graphs.

Assay of synthetic mixture formulation

Twenty synthetic mixture tablets were weighed and finely powdered. A quantity equivalent to 5 mg Amlodipine, 20 mg Olmesartan and 12.5 mg Chlorthalidone were transferred in to 100 ml volumetric flask and dissolved on about 25 ml methanol. The solution was ultrasonicated for 5 minutes and filtered through 0.45 μ whatmann filter paper no. 41. and the volume was made up to mark with same solvent. Above solution was taken to prepare a dilution of 50 μ g/ml of Amlodipine, 200 μ g/ml of Olmesartan and 125 μ g/ml of Chlorthalidone. The amount of drug was determined and three replicates were done. The result of assay was shown in table no. 10.

Method development and optimization

To develop a suitable method for the estimation of Amlodipine, Olmesartan and chlorthalidone by using different mobile phases were employed to achieve the best separation and resolution. The development was initiated with using a mobile phase of Phosphate buffer (pH-5) and methanol, (80:20 %v/v) was found to be appropriate allowing good separation and resolution of compound at a flow rate 1.0ml/min using Hypersil BDS C18 (4.6mm*250mm) 5 μ m column. In order to obtain a satisfactory and full detection for this new method, UV spectra of standard Amlodipine, Olmesartan and chlorthalidone solution were obtained. Based on Overlain Spectra of UV absorbance for Amlodipine, Olmesartan and chlorthalidone at 238 nm was chosen. Retention times were 5.503 min, 3.980 min and 3.107 min for Amlodipine, Olmesartan and Chlorthalidone respectively.

Method validation

The method was validated according to the ICH guidelines. The following validation characteristics were addressed: linearity, accuracy, precision, limit of detection, limit of quantitation and robustness.

System suitability testing (SST)

It is a part of chromatographic technique. These tests are used to prove that the resolution and reproducibility of the system are suitable for the analysis to be accomplished. It provides assurance that method will deliver accurate and precise data for its intended use. It involved test parameters as resolution, retention time, tailing factor and number of theoretical plate noted. The Result of system suitability testing was shown in table no. 1

Linearity

The linearity is expressed in term of correlation co-efficient of linear regression analysis. The linearity of response for Amlodipine, Olmesartan and Chlorthalidone was assessed by analysis of five independent levels of calibration curve in range of 2.5-7.5 μ g/ml, 6.25-18.75 μ g/ml and 10-30 μ g/ml for Amlodipine, Chlorthalidone and Olmesartan. The result of linearity was shown in table no. 2

Accuracy

The % recovery was performed by standard addition method. In these method fixed amount of sample mixture of Amlodipine, Chlorthalidone and Olmesartan and increasing amount of its working standard solutions were added at 80, 100 and 120% level of Amlodipine (2.0, 2.5 and 3.0 μ g/mL), Chlorthalidone(5,6.25 and 7.5 μ g/mL) and Olmesartan (8,10 and 12 μ g/mL). Area of peak obtained with each solution was measured for Amlodipine, Chlorthalidone and Olmesartan. The result of accuracy was shown in table no. 3, 4, 5.

Precision

Repeatability

In these for mixture solution of 50 μ g/ml of Amlodipine, 200 μ g/ml of Olmesartan and 125 μ g/ml of Chlorthalidone concentration were transferred into separate 10mL volumetric flask and dilute upto mark with mobile phase. The peak area was obtained with each solution was measured and % R.S.D was calculated. The result of repeatability was shown in table no.7.

Intraday precision

Mixed solutions containing 2.5-7.5 μ g/ml, 6.25-18.75 μ g/ml and 10-30 μ g/ml for Amlodipine, Chlorthalidone and Olmesartan, were analyzed on the same day and % R.S.D was calculated. The result of intraday precision was shown in table no. 6

Interday precision

Mixed solutions containing 2.5-7.5 μ g/ml, 6.25-18.75 μ g/ml and 10-30 μ g/ml for Amlodipine, Chlorthalidone and Olmesartan were analyzed on different days and % R.S.D was calculated. The result of interday precision was shown in table no. 6

Limit of Detection and Limit of Quantitation

The limit of detection (LOD) of the method refers to that minimum concentration of the active component that can be effectively estimated based on visual evaluation and the limit of quantitation (LOQ) is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample, which can be quantitatively determined with suitable precision and accuracy. The result of LOD and LOQ was shown in table no. 8. The LOD was estimated from the 5 calibration curves. The LOD may be calculated as

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times (\text{S.D.} / \text{Slope})$$

Where, S.D. = Standard deviation of the Y- intercepts of the 5 calibration curves

The LOQ was estimated from the calibration curves used to determine method linearity. The LOQ may be calculated as

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \times (\text{S.D./Slope})$$

Where, S.D. = Standard deviation of the Y- intercepts of the 5 calibration curves

Robustness

The solution containing concentration 50 µg/ml of Amlodipine, 200 µg/ml of Olmesartan and 125 µg/ml of Chlorthalidone was analyzed in different pH, mobile phase and flow rate. The peak area obtained with each solution was measured and % R.S.D was calculated. The result of robustness was shown in table no.9

RESULT AND DISCUSSION**Table 1: System Suitability Parameter.**

Sr No.	Name	Retention Time	Area	Resolution	Theoretical Plates
1	Amlodipine Besylate	5.503	656.691	5.976	8167
2	Chlorthalidone	3.107	948.600	0.00	7699
3	Olmesartan Medoxomil	3.980	1766.146	4.282	3575

Table 2: Linearity Study:

Sr. No.	Amlodipine Besylate			Chlorthalidone			Olmesartan Medoxomil		
	Conc. (µg/ml)	Peak area mean ± S.D (n=5)	% R.S.D	Conc. (µg/ml)	Peak area mean ± S.D (n=5)	% R.S.D	Conc. (µg/ml)	Peak area mean ± S.D (n=5)	% R.S.D
1	2.5	331.482 ± 5.16	1.55	6.25	478.261 ± 3.35	0.34	10	891.022 ± 6.19	0.69
2	3.75	494.008 ± 6.23	1.26	9.37	712.315 ± 12.13	1.70	15	1328.498 ± 9.60	0.72
3	5	645.026 ± 4.77	0.74	12.5	954.275 ± 7.21	0.75	20	1746.278 ± 12.14	0.69
4	6.25	823.473 ± 7.61	0.92	15.62	1157.369 ± 9.03	0.78	25	2214.655 ± 7.89	0.35
5	7.5	970.164 ± 9.98	1.08	18.75	1363.491 ± 7.25	0.53	30	2590.739 ± 13.17	0.50

Table 3: Accuracy study for Amlodipine Besylate.

Level	Amount of sample taken (µg/ml)	Amount of Standard Spiked (µg/ml)	Total Amount (µg/ml)	Amount Recovered (µg/ml)	% Recovery	Mean % Recovery ± S.D (n=3)	% RSD
80%	2.5	2	4.5	2.00	100.11	99.47 ± 0.55	0.56
	2.5	2	4.5	1.98	99.26		
	2.5	2	4.5	1.98	99.05		
100%	2.5	2.5	5	2.46	98.63	99.48 ± 1.38	1.39
	2.5	2.5	5	2.52	101.08		
	2.5	2.5	5	2.46	98.03		
120%	2.5	3	5.5	2.99	99.70	100.05 ± 1.04	1.04
	2.5	3	5.5	3.03	101.22		
	2.5	3	5.5	2.97	99.23		

Table 4: Accuracy study for Chlorthalidone.

Level	Amount of sample taken (µg/ml)	Amount of Standard Spiked (µg/ml)	Total Amount (µg/ml)	Amount Recovered (µg/ml)	% Recovery	Mean % Recovery ± S.D (n=3)	% RSD
80%	6.25	5	11.25	5.063	101.26	99.98 ± 1.16	1.16
	6.25	5	11.25	4.950	99.01		
	6.25	5	11.25	4.983	99.66		
100%	6.25	6.25	12.5	6.266	100.25	99.45 ± 0.69	0.701
	6.25	6.25	12.5	6.196	99.14		
	6.25	6.25	12.5	6.185	98.97		
120%	6.25	7.5	13.75	7.498	99.97	100.63 ± 0.70	0.702
	6.25	7.5	13.75	7.541	100.54		
	6.25	7.5	13.75	7.603	101.38		

Table 5: Accuracy study for Olmesartan Medoxomil.

Level	Amount of sample taken ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Amount of Standard Spiked ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Total Amount ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Amount Recovered ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	% Recovery	Mean % Recovery \pm S.D (n=3)	% RSD
80%	10	8	18	7.93	99.24	99.82 ± 0.54	0.5
	10	8	18	8.02	100.32		4
	10	8	18	7.99	99.89		
100%	10	10	20	9.86	98.63	98.65 ± 0.29	0.2
	10	10	20	9.83	98.37		9
	10	10	20	9.89	98.95		
120%	10	12	22	11.98	99.88	100.35 ± 1.23	1.2
	10	12	22	11.93	99.42		3
	10	12	22	12.21	101.76		

Table 6: Precision Study.

Drug	Conc. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Intraday precision		Interday precision	
		Mean \pm S.D (n=3)	%R.S.D	Mean \pm S.D (n=3)	% R.S.D
CHL	6.25	480.468 ± 1.67	0.349	481.88 ± 3.24	0.677
	12.5	944.149 ± 2.189	0.231	948.62 ± 6.39	0.673
	18.75	1376.788 ± 7.17	0.521	1372.57 ± 11.36	0.828
OLM	10	893.42 ± 1.84	0.206	885.61 ± 6.56	0.741
	20	1758.84 ± 3.53	0.201	1764.60 ± 14.87	0.842
	30	2637.26 ± 10.81	0.410	2632.988 ± 20.537	0.780
AML	2.5	331.25 ± 2.20	0.665	328.723 ± 3.952	1.202
	5	653.62 ± 1.51	0.232	650.722 ± 10.945	1.681
	7.5	980.33 ± 5.478	0.558	972.02 ± 17.30	1.780

Table 7: Repeatability Study.

Drug	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Peak area Mean \pm S.D (n=6)	% R.S.D
Amlodipine Besylate	5	655.999 ± 6.79	1.035
Chlorthalidone	12.5	951.046 ± 1.76	0.185
Olmessartan Meoxomil	20	1767.101 ± 9.08	0.513

Table 8: Results for LOD and LOQ.

Sr No.	Drug	LOD ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	LOQ ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)
1.	Amlodipine Besylate	2.087	6.325
2.	Chlorthalidone	0.738	2.238
3.	Olmesartan Meoxomil	0.874	2.650

Table 9: Robustness study for Amlodipine Besylate, Chlorthalidone and Olmesartan.

Parameters	Amlodipine Besylate	Chlorthalidone	Olmesartan Medoxomil	
Mobile Phase(+2%)	644.863	931.433	1734.297	
	82:18	643.556	929.55	1730.802
		631.03	933.265	1737.706
	Mean \pm S.D (n=3)	639.816 ± 7.63	931.416 ± 1.85	1734.268 ± 3.45
% RSD	1.19	0.19	0.19	
Mobile Phase (-2%)	671.147	9669.458	1804.943	
	78:22	668.465	965.56	1784.233
		671.126	969.424	1804.912
	Mean \pm S.D (n=3)	670.246 ± 1.542	968.147 ± 2.24	1798.029 ± 11.94
% RSD	0.230	0.231	0.664	
pH (+0.2 units)	653.261	948.484	1765.906	
	5.2	640.827	948.463	1746.987
		656.625	948.463	1742.726
	Mean \pm S.D (n=3)	650.237 ± 8.321	948.47 ± 0.012	1751.873 ± 12.33

pH (-0.2 units)	% RSD	1.279	0.001	0.704
		659.931	953.255	1774.92
	4.8	662.592	957.064	1782
		661.241	955.148	177.443
	Mean \pm S.D (n=3)	661.254 \pm 1.330	955.155 \pm 1.904	1778.454 \pm 3.540
Flow Rate (-0.2 units)	% RSD	0.201	0.199	0.199
		677.717	978.994	1822.655
	0.9	675.674	976.006	1803.334
		662.95	980.886	1826.252
	Mean \pm S.D (n=3)	672.137 \pm 8.001	978.628 \pm 2.460	1817.414 \pm 12.325
Flow Rate (+0.2 units)	% RSD	1.190	0.251	0.678
		638.291	921.968	1716.591
	1.2	640.834	925.655	1723.477
		638.919	922.877	1718.316
	Mean \pm S.D (n=3)	639.348 \pm 1.324	923.5 \pm 1.920	1719.461 \pm 3.583
	% RSD	0.207	0.207	0.208

Table 10: Optical Regression Characteristics and Validation Parameters.

Parameters	Amloipine Besylate	Chlorthalidone	Olmesartan Medoxomil
Detection Wavelength		238	
Calibration Range ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	2.5-7.5	6.25-18.75	10-30
Regression Equation ($y = mx + c$)	$Y=129.7x + 3.623$	$Y = 73.04x + 16.76$	$Y=86.85x + 14.28$
Slope (m)	129.7	73.04	86.85
Intercept (c)	3.623	16.76	14.28
Correlation Coefficient (r^2)	0.999	0.998	0.999
Limit of detection ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	2.087	0.738	0.874
Limit of Quantification ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	6.325	2.238	2.650

Table 11: Analysis of Marketed Formulation.

Sr. no	Label claim	Result (mg)	%Assay	Mean	SD	%RSD
1	12.5	12.43	99.47			
2	12.5	12.37	98.97	99.20	0.25	0.252
3	12.5	12.39	99.16			
4	20	19.92	99.62			
5	20	19.66	98.32	99.09	0.68	0.686
6	20	19.86	99.32			
7	5	4.98	99.74			
8	5	4.96	99.24	98.70	1.39	1.412
9	5	4.85	97.12			

FIGURES

Figure-1 Structure of Amlodipine Besylate.

Figure-2 Structure of Chlorthalidone.

Figure-3 Structure of Olmesartan Meoximil.

System Suitability

Figure 4 System Suitability Chromatogram.

Figure 5 Linearity of Chlorthalidone, Olmesartan and Amloipine.

Figure 6 Linearity Curve of Amlodipine Besylate.

Figure 7 Linearity Curve of Chlorthalidone.

Figure 8 Linearity Curve of Olmesartan.

DISCUSSION

Validation of an analytical method is the process by which it is established by laboratory studies and the performance characteristics of the method meet the requirements for the intended analytical application. Validation is required for any new or amended method to ensure that it is capable of giving reproducible and reliable results when used by different operators employing the same or different laboratories.

CONCLUSION

All the parameters are validated as per ICH guidelines for the method validation and found to be suitable for routine quantitative analysis in pharmaceutical dosage forms. The result of linearity, accuracy, precision proved to be within limits with lower limits of detection and quantification. Robustness of method was confirmed as no significant change was observed on analysis by subjecting the method to slight change in the method condition. Assay results obtained by proposed method are in fair agreement.

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